

Supporting Information for “Can we resolve the basin-scale sea level trend budget from GRACE ocean mass?”

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Contents of this file

1. Figures S1 to S4
2. Tables S1 to S2

Introduction This Supplementary Information provides additional Figures and the full region-mean and global-mean sea-level trends from Figure 3 in Table S1 and from Figure 5 in Table S2. (The full region-mean and global-mean sea-level trends relative to Figure 4 are given in Table 1 in the main text.)

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Figure S1. Spatial difference in trend (EWH, mm y^{-1}) between the ICE6G and Geruo A GIA models used to correct GRACE ocean mass.

Figure S2. The wavelength spectra from different data products of (a) directly-observed sea level trends (b) steric sea level trends and (c) mass sea level trends.

Figure S3. Spherical harmonic degree-variance for the directly-observed sea level from satellite altimetry (black), steric (red) and mass (blue) trends, and the discrepancy between the directly-observed and steric plus mass sea level trends (thick grey), to compare with Figure 2.

Figure S4. Sensitivity of SSH trend (mm y^{-1}) to spatial masking and method of trend calculation. (a) Ocean basins between 65° latitude with the 300 km land buffer masked in grey, (b) ocean basins with the 300 km buffer from land and poor data coverage or high variability masked in grey, (c) observed SSH trend from ESA SLCCI satellite altimetry (coloured by region) and (d) trend anomaly between the sum of ISAS15 shallow steric, deep steric and JPL RL06 GRACE SSH trend, and ESA SLCCI satellite altimetry SSH trend. Coloured error bars and shaded regions in (c,d) represent 1σ (dark) and 2σ (light) trend standard error for the satellite altimetry and quadratic sum of GRACE and steric trend standard error. Grey error bars and shaded regions in (c,d) represent the 2σ sum in quadrature of trend standard error, spread in data products and spread in other data processing shown in Figure 4. The basin trends are ordered as (d) Atlantic Ocean, (e) Pacific Ocean, (f) Indian Ocean and (g) global mean.

Table S1. Region-mean and global-mean sea-level trend by varying products. Sea-level trend from time series mean Jan 2005–Dec 2015 and 1σ trend standard error ($\text{mm } y^{-1}$).

Product	GIA	S Atl	Ind-S Pac	Region			Global	
				E Pac	SP N Atl	ST N Atl		NW Pac
<i>Shallow Steric (ARGO)</i>								
EN4.2.1		1.5 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.7	-0.8 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.5	-2.4 ± 0.5	1.2 ± 0.1
Scripps		1.1 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.7	-1.2 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.5	-1.9 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.1
ISAS15		0.8 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.7	-0.4 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 0.5	-2.2 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.1
JAMSTEC		1.3 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.8	0.9 ± 0.3	3.8 ± 0.5	-3.0 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.1
Ensemble Mean		1.2 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.7	-0.5 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.5	-2.2 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.1
<i>Deep Steric</i>								
WCRP		-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1 ± 0.1
EN4.2.1		0.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	-0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	-0.1 ± 0.1
ECCO		-0.5 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
<i>Mass (GRACE)</i>								
GSFC	Geruo A	2.3 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.3	3.8 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1
JPL RL05	Geruo A	2.3 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.2	2.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.1
JPL RL06	ICE6G	1.8 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.1
ISAS15 + WCRP + JPL RL06		2.7 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.2	4.6 ± 0.7	0.8 ± 0.3	5.5 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 0.1
<i>Observed by altimetry</i>								
ESA SLCCI		2.7 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.8	1.1 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.4	3.1 ± 0.1
AVISO		2.6 ± 0.2	3.9 ± 0.1	5.0 ± 0.8	1.6 ± 0.2	6.4 ± 0.5	0.6 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.1
MEASURES		2.3 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 0.9	0.6 ± 0.2	6.1 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 0.2
CSIRO		2.3 ± 0.0	3.9 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.8	0.8 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.6	1.2 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 0.1
WCRP ^a mass		-	-	-	-	-	-	2.3 ± 0.2
WCRP ^b steric		-	-	-	-	-	-	1.3 ± 0.4
WCRP ^b mass + steric		-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6 ± 0.4
WCRP ^b altimetry		-	-	-	-	-	-	3.5 ± 0.2

Note: Sea-level trend and 1σ trend standard error, 300 km buffer from land, time series mean, Jan 2005–Dec 2015 ($\text{mm } y^{-1}$)

^a. Ensemble mean in Table 11 of WCRP, 2018

^b. Ensemble mean in Table 13 of WCRP, 2018

Table S2. Region-mean and global-mean sea-level trend by varying data quality mask. Sea-level trend from time series mean Jan 2005–Dec 2015 and 1σ trend standard error ($\text{mm } y^{-1}$).

Product	Mask	Region						Global
		S Atl	Ind-S Pac	E Pac	SP N Atl	STN Atl	NW Pac	
<i>Shallow Steric (ARGO)</i>								
ISAS15	Buffer	0.8 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.7	-0.4 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 0.5	-2.2 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.1
ISAS15	High Quality	0.7 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.7	-0.4 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.4	-2.9 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.1
<i>Mass (GRACE)</i>								
JPL RL06, ICE6G GIA	Buffer	1.8 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.1
JPL RL06, ICE6G GIA	High Quality	1.7 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.1
<i>Observed by altimetry</i>								
ESA SLCCI	Buffer	2.7 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.8	1.1 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.4	3.1 ± 0.1
ESA SLCCI	High Quality	2.9 ± 0.2	4.5 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.9	1.1 ± 0.2	6.0 ± 0.4	-0.4 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.1

Note: Sea-level trend and 1σ trend standard error, time series mean, Jan 2005–Dec 2015 ($\text{mm } y^{-1}$)